

Rapid Deployment of Visual Path Following via Average Representation

Zdeněk Rozsympálek^{*1} · Tomáš Rouček¹ · Jiří Ulrich · ¹ Tomáš Krajník¹

Preprint

Abstract The advances in deep learning for image processing greatly impacted mobile robots’ ability to navigate using vision-based techniques. There are many applications in which the robot is required to follow a specific visual cue. One newly emerging method for autonomous navigation along a consistent visual cue is Visual Teach and Generalise (VTAG). It is a unified approach to extract suitable features for path following in repetitive and structured environments. However, a relatively large number of data samples is required for the time-consuming training of a detector tied to a specific visual cue. We introduce an improved version of VTAG that does not need any neural network training and significantly reduces the requirements for the number of data samples. The core idea is to use an average representation of images collected during short supervised traversals, capturing characteristics of repetitive paths. The average representation is created in a latent space crafted by contrastive learning with the linear matching scheme and can be computed in real time, even on a CPU. The capability of rapid deployment, precision, and robustness of the presented method is evaluated in multiple field experiments performed in different environments.

Keywords Path Following · Visual Navigation · Machine Learning in Robotics

1 Introduction

Mobile robotics has emerged as a hot research topic, driven by the increasing demand for autonomous systems operating in various environments. The advent of advanced sensing technologies, coupled with improvements in computing

Fig. 1: Our method creates an average representation from T training images. This representation is then cross-correlated with a live camera feed. The resulting histogram is used to control the robot’s heading during navigation.

power, has enabled robots to understand their surroundings, make decisions, and perform tasks autonomously.

Many mobile robots are equipped with cameras, as they are light, cheap, and low-power. However, long-term appearance changes and repetitive environments pose major challenges to vision-based mapping and localisation methods [1]. These challenges led to the development of vision-based navigation methods that do not require building of consistent metric maps for navigation.

Visual Teach and Repeat (VT&R) [2] methods strictly divide mapping and navigation into two phases. An operator manually guides the robot in the teaching phase along a desired trajectory. In the repeat phase, the robot follows

¹Czech Technical University in Prague, FEE, Czech Republic
*E-mail: rozsyzde@fel.cvut.cz

the recorded trajectory using previously captured visual features. Visual servoing-based variants of VT&R simplify the navigation stack by utilising image sequences instead of metric maps, eradicating errors associated with traditional mapping. These approaches reduce the requirements on the robustness of the feature matching [3] while keeping the navigation error bounded [4,5]. The handling of environmental variations is critical for long-term, reliable navigation [6], and VT&R is an attractive framework thanks to its robustness.

VT&R methods are reliable and easy to deploy, but manually guiding the robot through every possible path is time-consuming, e.g., [7] mentions that mapping a 0.08 km² urban park took four days. To speed up the mapping, some researchers augmented map-based VT&R with vision-based path following [8]. However, the time reduction in mapping was offset by the time required to design and tune detectors for repetitive paths.

Many environments where the deployment of mobile robots would be highly beneficial, such as warehouses, automated farms, or hotels, are composed of elements of similar appearance. The framework that takes advantage of the repetitiveness of visual elements within the VT&R paradigm is called Visual Teach and Generalise (VTAG) [9]. Instead of mapping the entire environment, the VTAG framework creates a detector of an arbitrary visual cue (representing a typical path) consistent throughout the training set. This enables the robot to follow previously untraversed paths, effectively removing the need to map the entire operational area while preserving the simplicity and robustness of VT&R [5]. The deployment scenarios suitable for VTAG are further specified in Section 3.2. The existing VTAG method can reduce the mapping time, but still requires a large number of data samples used for time-consuming neural network fine-tuning on a specialised computational server.

In this paper, we present a method that can create a detector of repetitive visual cue on the fly, making it available instantaneously after the teaching phase. Instead of the fine-tuned neural network detecting the visual cue, we use an aggregated robust representation for the path traversal. The method not only eliminates the neural network fine-tuning, but also reduces the number of required training images by two orders of magnitude. A diagram describing the presented method is shown in Figure 1. The simplification of the deployment process compared to the current version of VTAG is visualised in Figure 4.

To summarise, our main contribution is that the presented method offers similar functionality as the original approach [9] while:

- a) Removing the requirement for fine-tuning the neural network to follow a visual cue.
- b) Significantly reducing the number of map images required for a successful traversal.

- c) Speeding up the deployment process by creating a representation of a visual cue in real-time.
- d) Demonstrating capabilities of VTAG in multiple scenarios with extended autonomy.

The contribution (d) mainly extends the trustworthiness of the generalisation capability of the method, (a), (b), and (c) improve usability by reducing the deployment time as the neural network does not need to be fine-tuned any more. Additionally, without fine-tuning, we can avoid unpredictable changes of the latent space and enhance the reproducibility.

In this paper, we first discuss relevant research and existing methods. Then, we define the symbolism and terminology required to describe the proposed approach. This formalism is used to identify suitable deployment scenarios and provide a theoretical reasoning to support the validity of the method. We also discuss the benefits arising from applying the presented approach in existing navigation stacks. Finally, we report the results and quantitative analysis of multiple experiments in various deployment scenarios.

2 Related Work

A substantial body of research focuses on detecting and following a specific visual cue. In these applications, the robot can exploit the consistent structure of the environment and follow a certain feature, such as a road, wall, or line. Historically, these systems used single-purpose detectors that relied on a distinct colour [10,11] or shape [12] of a given feature. Some approaches also employ pre-trained segmentation models [13]. These methods are often tied to use in a specific domain and are not approached as a general framework for arbitrary visual cues. More recent approaches can use weakly supervised or reinforcement learning to follow the path. However, these methods usually require large datasets [9,14], simulated environments [15,16], time-consuming training, and powerful hardware. In contrast, the VT&R methods are based on one-shot evaluation and can follow arbitrary visual features. VTAG directly extends VT&R to navigate the robot along the unseen paths, containing a consistent visual cue.

The method presented in this paper extends a type of VT&R, often called appearance-based or bearing-only [4]. This type of VT&R simplifies the visual part of the framework. Under the assumptions presented in [5], it is not necessary to obtain a full 6DoF transformation between live and map images. Instead, it is sufficient to obtain only a horizontal displacement between these two images [17,2]. Obtaining a precise and reliable 6DoF transformation between two images requires multiple keypoint correspondences, whereas, in theory, the horizontal displacement estimation can be done with a single correspondence. This horizontal displacement is then used to correct the heading of the ground robot and

steer it towards the desired trajectory. [18] shows that it is possible to replace keypoint matching schemes with the cross-correlation operator. There are other VT&R methods [19, 20] that rely on consistent metric maps and are less related to the method presented in this article.

When we aim for long-term autonomous deployment, the robot has to solve unexpected situations. Primarily, it must be able to avoid collisions during navigation. This is typically addressed by reactive behaviours at the lower level [21, 22]. Another issue is changing the appearance of the environment, which can cause a malfunction of the visual part of a navigation system. At first, researchers focused on hand-crafting descriptors robust to variations in point of view and illumination [23, 24, 25]. With the boom of machine learning in vision, it became apparent that the feature descriptor must be trained rather than hand-crafted [26, 27]. Especially in the case of outdoor environments, it is challenging to create a robust descriptor without learning from the data due to common dynamics, e.g. seasonal, day&night changes [28, 29, 30, 31, 32].

One of the promising areas of research that can produce a useful representation of input data is contrastive learning. These representations exist in a latent space created during the training process. The result of the training process is typically a function with learned parameters that transform the input into a latent space where similar data points are located close together. The similarity definition is usually task-specific. Models using contrastive learning are commonly referred to as Siamese because they consist of two branches with shared model parameters and different inputs [33]. The Siamese networks are suitable for robot localisation because they are explicitly designed for one-shot evaluation.

A popular application of a fully convolutional Siamese neural network is tracking objects [34]. This training method creates a spatially consistent representation of an image that can be used to track an object extracted in a one-shot manner. Further research proved that altering this learning method can create a robust feature-matching pipeline. This research refers to the descriptor as a hypercolumn, and the image representation is a dense set of spatially consistent hypercolumns [35]. The major disadvantage of these methods is that they require annotated datasets. The hypercolumn method exploits auto-annotation based on the structure from motion methods; thus, correspondences still need to be obtained before training. Labelling is a major obstacle when working with large datasets. Self-supervised methods are a promising approach to avoid extensive labelling. Many of these architectures are built on contrastive learning approaches [36, 37]. They are not learning similarities using annotation, but instead using a proxy task for the training.

The first version of VTAG builds on a self-supervised learning paradigm and was introduced in [9]. It exploits the dense representation matching pipeline [38] and the appearance-

based approach used in VT&R navigation [2, 4]. The goal of the VTAG framework is to automatically extract distinct visual cues typical for the operational environment and use them for path following. Automatic feature extraction is achieved by collecting a dataset with a consistent position of visual cues in the image space. The dataset is used to train a neural network that produces dense image representations, which contain robust descriptors of a visual cue. The main problem is that the time saved by eliminating the need to map the whole area is offset by the optimisation of the neural network. Moreover, to fine-tune the neural network, collecting a large number (thousands) of images is still necessary.

Fig. 2: Standard navigation stack for appearance based VT&R methods. VTAG can replace maps of some edges in the topological map. The parts of the stack studied in this paper are highlighted in red.

The established navigation stacks exploiting the VT&R methods usually rely on non-metric topological maps. The nodes are places important for the robot application scenario, and the edges are traversable paths. The edges are manually mapped to collect the images, which are used by the VT&R to perform the autonomous navigation. The VTAG fits into this paradigm and can be used to traverse the unmapped edges. The purpose of VT&R and VTAG is to provide a simple and robust high-level method to steer the robot along the planned path. It does not provide any traversability estimates or collision avoidance. Lower-level behaviours of the navigation stack must address these problems. The diagram showing such a navigation stack is shown in Figure 2. This approach is called navigation without localisation. In practice, the robot does not need to estimate its position with high precision. Usually, it is sufficient to reach the desired position within a certain distance and then activate task-specific behaviour, which handles the precise control.

3 Method Description

This section provides a detailed description of the method presented. First, formal definitions must be made to allow for the description of the framework. All the notation used

for description of the method is summarised in Table 4. The goal is to follow a long path with consistent visual cues (fence, line) or structure (sidewalk, corridor). We call the path that fulfils this property a **desired path**. Traditionally, a map of the entire desired path must be created for a reliable traversal. Mapping long paths can be undesirable for various reasons, such as time and memory requirements. Instead of the time-consuming mapping, we only collect data over a short subsection of the desired path. We refer to this subsection as **training path**. The presented version of VTAG consists of three steps:

1. Manually traverse the training path (subsection of the desired path).
2. Transform the training images to the latent space and create the average representation.
3. Use the average representation to navigate the robot through the desired path.

In the following subsections, we describe the visual model used in this paper, we elaborate on each of the three deployment steps, and we discuss the benefits arising from using the average representation.

3.1 VTAG Image Processing Model

This paper uses the latent space of a publicly available model trained and presented in previous work [38]. Previous research shows that it is possible to use a well-designed proxy task to train a convolutional Siamese neural network with a latent space suitable for horizontal displacement estimation. The proxy task used to train the model is to estimate the horizontal coordinate of an image cutout. The training scheme is similar to [34], but emphasises the application for ground mobile robots. Data pairs are two images with the same position and heading, but taken under different conditions (day&night, seasonal) to make the latent space robust to environmental dynamics and avoid neural network collapse.

For inference, the images are not cropped, but one is extended by circular padding to evaluate all possible horizontal shifts exhaustively. The estimated horizontal shift between the map and live images provides a steering correction, navigating the robot along the desired path. In other words, the robot needs to adjust its heading to ensure a perfect horizontal overlap of the map and live images. Following this behaviour leads to convergence towards the mapped trajectory. The evaluation process is defined as:

$$\vec{h} = f(I_A) \star P(f(I_B)), \quad (1)$$

where I is the notion for input images, and f is the trained convolutional neural network (CNN). The CNN output is the image representation, which can be extended by horizontal

circular padding P and cross-correlated (\star) with other representations. Since both representations have the same height, the output vector \vec{h} contains one value for every possible horizontal displacement between images. The architecture of CNN is described in Table 1. All convolutional filters have size 3×3 . The trained model is taken directly from the previous work [38].

Table 1: CNN architecture

Layer	Elements	Shape CH \times H \times W
Input	Image	$3 \times 320 \times 512$
Layer 1	Conv, BN, ReLu, Max Pool	$16 \times 160 \times 256$
Layer 2	Conv, BN, ReLu, Max Pool	$64 \times 80 \times 128$
Layer 3	Conv, BN, ReLu, Max Pool	$256 \times 40 \times 64$
Layer 4	Conv, BN, ReLu, Max Pool	$512 \times 20 \times 64$
Output	Conv	$16 \times 6 \times 64$

3.2 Mapping Requirements

We refer to the image collection process over the training path as mapping. The result of the mapping is a representation of visual features relevant for navigation. These must be consistently present across the collected images, while irrelevant features must exhibit significant variation and diversity. Therefore, the training path must meet the following conditions:

1. Training path shares consistent visual features with the unseen desired path.
2. The visual features are located at a consistent position in the image space of training images.
3. The training images are diverse enough to distinguish navigation-relevant and navigation-irrelevant features.

The requirement 1 limits VTAG to usage in repetitive environments. When there is no consistent visual cue along the whole desired path, using an aggregated representation for reliable traversal is impossible. Next, requirement 2 places a constraint on the precision of image collection. Usually, the goal is to maintain a certain distance from a visual cue during autonomous navigation. For example, keep the robot in the middle of the sidewalk or one meter left of the fence. This desired goal must be met during data collection. Otherwise, the visual feature is not located at a consistent position in the image space, resulting in a noisy map representation and unreliable navigation. From our experience, it is easy to manually control the robot and obtain a useful average representation.

Finally, requirement 3 is introduced to ensure that the only consistent feature in the training images is similar to the desired path. It is necessary that the only consistent visual feature in the training images belongs to the chosen visual

Fig. 3: Hypercolumn cells overlaid over the image. Each cell in R is represented by a descriptor \vec{q} with coordinates x, y .

cue. Otherwise, the created representation can then navigate the robot towards the undesired features (i.e. background) instead of following a given visual cue. We collect images from both the front and rear cameras to address this issue. The images taken by the rear camera are horizontally flipped to comply with the requirement 2. This extends the diversity of training images and mitigates the influence of the background. Alternatively, it is possible to use a longer training path, which also reduces the requirement for data collection precision. The minimal required length of the training path is heavily influenced by the spatial properties of the environment.

3.3 Average Representation

All processing is performed in a spatially consistent latent space, which is robust to the changing appearance of the scene. The representation R of the image I is obtained as $R = f(I)$, where f is a CNN from [38], previously discussed in this section. CNN transforms the input image of size $512 \times 320 \times 3$ into a representation of size $64 \times 6 \times 16$. To comply with established terminology, we refer to each spatial vector as a hypercolumn [35]. Each hypercolumn encodes the image pixels at specific image coordinates. In our case, the hypercolumns \vec{q} are vectors of size 16 and the representation of width w and height h can be written as:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{q}_{1,1} & \cdots & \vec{q}_{w,1} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vec{q}_{1,h} & \cdots & \vec{q}_{w,h} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The visualisation of the receptive fields of individual hypercolumns is shown in Figure 3. For our purposes, the representation is significantly denser in the x -axis to allow a precise horizontal matching.

We can think of the desired path as a set of consecutive images that can be encountered during its traversal. The representations are obtained by passing the images through the

CNN. We denote a set of all representations along the desired path as \mathcal{R}^d . The problem is that during data collection, we do not traverse the whole desired path; we only traverse a representative subsection. The set of T training representations collected during the mapping is denoted as:

$$\mathcal{R}^t = \{R_1^t, R_2^t, \dots, R_T^t\}. \quad (3)$$

Finally, we define a set of all possible existing representations as \mathcal{R} .

In theory, for a reliable traversal, we need to find an optimal representation R^* . This optimal representation should maximise the response (in our case, the cross-correlation) to all representations in \mathcal{R}^d and minimise the response to all existing representations not present in the desired path $\mathcal{R} \setminus \mathcal{R}^d$. Formalized, we want R^* to have following properties:

$$\text{Maximize: } \sum_{R^d \in \mathcal{R}^d} (R^* \star R^d) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Minimize: } \sum_{R \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \mathcal{R}^d} (R^* \star R). \quad (5)$$

The representation tensors are the same size; thus, the cross-correlation outputs a scalar. In practice, this is not a tractable optimisation task. First, given the nature of our use case, the whole set \mathcal{R}^d is not available. We only have information about the desired path from the sample set \mathcal{R}^t . Secondly, the set of all existing representations \mathcal{R} is extremely large.

The first optimization task (4) is addressed by the mapping requirements 1 and 2. All representations in \mathcal{R}^d must contain a feature (hypercolumn) $\vec{q}_{x,y}$, which is also present in the representations from \mathcal{R}^t at the same position x, y . When this requirement is fulfilled, the visual cue is consistent with the target path and present in the training images. The second optimisation task (5) is addressed by the mapping requirement 3. We use the robot rear camera with a horizontally flipped output to collect as diverse \mathcal{R}^t as possible. When all three requirements are met, it is possible to use representations from \mathcal{R}^t to obtain an approximation of R^* .

Our approach exploits two important properties of the latent space crafted in previous work. Firstly, the CNN output is robust to various disturbances, such as sensor noise and environmental dynamics. Secondly, the cross-correlation of representations directly estimates the log-likelihood of similarity between the two input images:

$$\log \mathcal{L}(I_a, I_b) = f(I_a) \star f(I_b). \quad (6)$$

Similarity in the path following task means that the images are taken at the same place with the same heading. The neural network used is trained directly to produce a latent space fulfilling both conditions as shown in (1).

Considering the training images as independent observations, we can use the maximum likelihood estimate for the live image I^l to be a good match with all training representations:

$$\log\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{R}^t|I^l) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T \log\mathcal{L}(I^l, I_k^t), \quad (7)$$

where T is the number of training images. The latent space is crafted to compute the log-likelihood of similarities via cross-correlation as in (6). Thus, the likelihood estimate can be rewritten as follows.

$$\log\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{R}^t|I^l) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T R^l \star R_k^t. \quad (8)$$

The cross-correlation is a linear operation, and the live representation can be moved outside the sum.

$$\log\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{R}^t|I^l) = R^l \star \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T R_k^t. \quad (9)$$

In this form, we can already see that the average map representation naturally arises from the maximum likelihood estimate. We define the average representation R^{avg} as:

$$R^{avg} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T R_k^t. \quad (10)$$

Finally, when the average representation is plugged into the maximum likelihood estimate, we end up with the final form:

$$\log\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{R}^t|I^l) = R^l \star R^{avg}. \quad (11)$$

The experiments show that the average representation can be a good approximation of the optimal representation for the desired path traversal $R^* \approx R^{avg}$ when the mapping requirements are met.

Intuitively, the average representation preserves the features consistent in the training images, and the inconsistent parts of the images yield a noisy feature that does not match any real-world objects. Note that by averaging the feature, we do not want to estimate its expected value. That would require the features to be normally distributed in the latent space, which is not the case. We sometimes refer to features as "similar", but our matching scheme does not evaluate the distance between the features. The "similarity" rather means that the correlation of two features yields a high value. Thus, using the average representation is agnostic to the feature distribution.

Ultimately, the choice of a linear matching scheme allows us to create a simple aggregated representation of the training path. Standard non-linear matching schemes such as L2 or cosine distance would not allow moving live images outside the sum in (9). The presented derivation shows that

using average representation with a linear matching scheme is equivalent to evaluating the live image against all the training images.

3.4 Navigation

The navigation step relies on horizontal image displacement estimation via cross-correlation as in (1). The robot should start in a position where the consistent feature is visible. Then, a constant forward velocity is set, and only the heading rotation velocity is controlled by the VTAG. When the live image representation R^l and the map representation R^{avg} overlap perfectly (there is no displacement), the robot traverses the trajectory well, and no heading correction is needed. This is usually not the case in practice, and corrections are necessary in cases where the robot is misplaced, poorly controlled, or the desired path is curved.

The heading correction ω applied to steer the robot through the desired path is calculated as:

$$\vec{h} = P(R^{avg}) \star R^l, \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta p = \operatorname{argmax}(\vec{h}) - \frac{w_r}{2}, \quad (13)$$

$$\omega = k \cdot \Delta p, \quad (14)$$

where P is a circular padding added to the representation in the horizontal dimension. We use the padding of size $\frac{w_r}{2}$, where w_r is the width of the representation. The index of the maximal bin in the vector \vec{h} is used to obtain the horizontal displacement Δp . Finally, (14) is used to obtain the heading correction ω regulated by a tunable proportional constant k that can adjust the aggressivity of the control. Note that the distance of visual features limits the convergence speed and can not be easily improved by tuning or altering the regulator. The regulator controls only the robot's heading, where reference is the direction of the followed features. Convergence towards the desired trajectory is a phenomenon emerging from this strategy and cannot be directly controlled. The properties of appearance-based methods are widely discussed in previous research [4,5].

3.5 Benefits of Average Representation

This subsection highlights features that naturally arise from using the average representation. These features can be beneficial in multiple autonomous deployment scenarios and do not require changes to the standard navigation stack.

3.5.1 Real-time Feature Engineering and Interpretability

The major benefit of our approach is that it can be deployed in real-time for an arbitrary consistent visual cue. The av-

erage representation can be accumulated during teleoperated traversal and immediately evaluated with live histogram plotting. This online feature selection can reduce person-hours, which have to be spent by computer vision engineers to design the detector of the visual cue. Such a task often requires highly skilled workers, and reducing their workload can result in cheaper deployments.

Moreover, in some scenarios, it is not obvious how the one-purpose detector should be designed. For example, traversing the sandy pathway (as in Section 4.3) can be implemented in multiple different ways, e.g. detecting the boundaries of the pathway, segmenting the sandy surface, and many more. Our approach removes these design choices from the process by exploiting the entire image and extracting the most consistent and reliable features. The proposed simplification of the workflow is presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Diagram presenting different workflows of previous work [9] and presented method. The average representation enables significant simplification of the deployment process. Using a server to train a new neural network for every visual cue is no longer necessary.

Using our method as a black box can make it difficult to interpret the outputs of the created detector. It is always beneficial to have insight into the decision-making of the system so that the engineer can predict the robot’s behaviour in various edge cases. The spatial consistency representa-

tion makes it possible to evaluate how different parts of the image contribute to the output. The likelihood of all possible displacements (12) can be rewritten using the summation notation as:

$$\vec{h}[d] = \sum_{i=1}^c \sum_{j=1}^h \sum_{k=1}^w P(R^{avg})[i, j, k + d] \cdot R^l[i, j, k], \quad (15)$$

where c, h, w are the representation’s channels, height and width, respectively. The matching scheme uses summation over the spatial dimensions to calculate the similarity of the whole representation. When we want to see the contribution of a hypercolumn (bin) representing a section of the image, we can set the displacement d as a fixed value and omit the summation over the spatial dimensions. Final contribution matrix C is computed as:

$$C[j, k] = \sum_{i=1}^c P(R^{avg})[i, j, k + d] \cdot R^l[i, j, k], \quad (16)$$

where the indices $j = y, k = x$ now correspond to the spatial position of the hypercolumn $q_{x,y}$. Note that d is fixed at the value that produces the maximal likelihood in (15). Contributions directly quantify the similarity of individual hypercolumns. The visualisation of this approach is shown in Figure 10. The CNN significantly squeezes the height dimension, which makes the contribution less precise in the vertical axis.

3.5.2 Semantic Localisation

Another benefit of our method is based on the fact that the Siamese networks are designed for one-shot evaluation. The cross-correlation outputs higher values when the two representations are well-matched. The likelihood estimate can be reversed so that we can find the best set of training representations that matches the current live image $\log \mathcal{L}(I^l | \mathcal{R}^t)$. This property extends the versatility to the entire framework. The live representation R^l can be cross-correlated with multiple average representations. The representation R^{avg} that produces the highest likelihood can be chosen to control the robot.

This simple concept can extend the framework’s usability, e.g., in multi-experience-based navigations like [39, 40]. The feasibility of this approach was already demonstrated in our previous work [41]. We also used semantic localisation in our experiments, as shown in Figures 12 and 15. Note that semantic localisation in its current form can not directly estimate a precise metric position of the robot.

4 Experiments

Five experiments were conducted to evaluate the capabilities of the improved VTAG framework. Each experiment

Fig. 5: Photos of the robots used in the experiments.

takes place in a different type of environment. The mobile robot used for experiments 1 and 2 is the Boston Dynamics Spot. Experiments 3, 4 and 5 were conducted with the Clearpath Jackal. Both robots have Basler Ace 2 a2A1920-51 cameras facing forward and backwards. The Jackal robot has one more camera facing to the left. All cameras stream 1080p video at 40FPS, resized to 512×320 for processing. The Spot robot uses an Intel NUC i7 9th Gen, and the Jackal robot uses the NVIDIA Jetson AGX Orin. Additionally, the ground truth for experiments 1 and 2 is provided by the LiDAR Ouster OS1. The robotic platforms can be seen in Figure 5. The processing speed and comparison to the previous work are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Methods comparison

	VTG [9]	OUR
CNN size (params)		1.4M
CNN forward pass (NUC)		50ms
CNN forward pass (ORIN)		15ms
Required image num.	thousands	tens
Representation building	hours/days	real-time
Descriptor size	16MB	100KB

The Spot robot uses proprietary software for collision avoidance and traversability estimation. It is impossible to turn off these low-level behaviours for safety reasons enforced by the manufacturer. Our framework provides a higher level of control to navigate the robot along the desired path.

4.1 Experiment 1: Corridor Traversal

In the first experiment, we show the convergence properties and applicability in an indoor environment. The goal is to use VTAG to keep the robot centred in the middle while walking forward through a corridor. The experiment is conducted in the FEE CTU building in Prague on the Charles Square campus. The building has most corridors with roughly similar dimensions but different appearances

caused by wall colours, furniture, and window placements. In the experiment, we create a map representation based on the traversal through the centre of one corridor, and test it in two other corridors. The mapping traversal is 15m long, and we collect two images (front and rear) per meter, so the average representation of the campus corridor consists of 30 images in total. All corridors traversed during the experiment are shown in Figure 6.

Using the methodology proposed in [4, 5, 41], we place the robot at the beginning of each corridor with the heading and lateral displacement of ≈ 1 m from the corridor centre. Then, the system autonomously navigates the robot through the corridor. According to the model specified in [4, 5], the robot’s heading is corrected almost instantaneously, and lateral displacement (from the centre of the corridor) gradually converges to zero as the robot traverses the corridor. As noted above, the convergence speed is mainly constrained by the structure of the environment.

Fig. 6: The two top images are examples taken by the robot in the mapped corridor 2. The two bottom images are from not mapped corridors 1 and 3.

LiDAR data were recorded during the traversals to quantify the convergence. We use RANSAC [42] to find two collinear lines 3 m apart representing the corridor’s walls. When the position of the walls is estimated, it is possible to calculate the robot’s lateral displacement from the corridor’s centre. Since the corridors are not exactly the same width, and the LiDAR is placed on top of the walking robot, the precision of the ground truth is about 0.1m. Additionally, the navigation is influenced by the limited precision of the teleoperated image collection. The displacements from the centre of the corridor during the traversals are shown in Figure 7. The mean absolute error of corridor centre traversal is 0.07 ± 0.04 m. This value is computed from measurements collected after 10 m of traverse, where the robot has already corrected the introduced displacement.

Fig. 7: Convergence to the centre of the various corridors using one corridor representation.

4.2 Experiment 2: Rail Following

The second experiment is conducted in an urban outdoor environment along the banks of the Vltava River in Prague. The experiment investigates whether it is possible to use the proposed method to navigate over non-trivial paths while performing semantic localisation. The goal is to keep a defined distance from the railing and traverse a long path along the river. The sidewalk consists of different surfaces and is lined with a railing. The appearance of the railing varies slightly throughout the desired path. We mapped around 20 m of the path along the railing and traversed a trajectory of 500 m back and forth, resulting in over a kilometre-long traversal with a single manual turn by 180 deg at the end. The desired path consists of two distinct sections. One-half closely resembles the training path with a bicycle lane, but the second-half has a different surface and railing. The chosen place is relatively busy, and the navigation stack has to deal with pedestrians and cyclists in the camera view. Furthermore, the desired path has a significant curvature, and there is a challenging situation B where the railing diverges from the bike lane. The whole trajectory is visualised in Figure 8.

Fig. 8: Trajectory visualisation. The image is only illustrative and does not represent any measured data. The aerial imagery is taken from mapy.com. The places highlighted in blue refer to challenging situations A and B during traversal.

Training images are collected by manually controlling the robot at a fixed distance from the railing (0.9 m). The images were taken once per meter and used to create the average representation. When the representation is created, we take the robot to the start of the desired path and let the framework perform the traversal. The beginning of the desired path looks similar to the training trajectory except for the background. However, after ≈ 250 m, the appearance changes significantly. Figure 9 shows training images and images from challenging sections of the desired path.

Fig. 9: The two top images are samples of training images. The rear camera image must be horizontally flipped to create a consistent representation. The two bottom images show sections of the desired path with different appearances.

In Figure 11, we report the ground truth distance to the railing measured by LiDAR and the estimated horizontal displacement used for heading correction throughout the traversal. The robot can successfully keep the defined distance with two exceptions. Firstly, after traversing ≈ 30 m (situation A), collision avoidance is activated to avoid a pedestrian. The robot deviates from the path and then autonomously converges back. Secondly, the robot enters the challenging section at a distance of ≈ 250 m. The system chooses to follow the bike lane instead of the railing, resulting in a smoother trajectory (situation B). Note that the railing is not a dense surface, adding noise to the ground truth estimate. The second half of the desired path also contains gaps in the railing, as shown in Figure 9. These gaps further degrade the ground truth quality and are visible in the reported lateral displacements.

In this experiment, we also showcase the additional features of the framework. Firstly, semantic localisation is used to estimate the rotation of the robot. We have two representations, one with the railing on the left-hand side and one horizontally flipped. The robot evaluates both representations simultaneously and chooses the best-matching representation for heading adjustments. This concept allows us to traverse

Fig. 10: The left image is from the training set, and the other two images show the traversal section with the appearance change shown in Figure 9. The contribution matrix C is linearly interpolated and used as an overlay. The numbers at image axes mark the pixel coordinates, and the overlaid colour palette depicts the likelihood match [-] of the given hypercolumn.

the desired path in both directions without manually specifying the traversal direction. The estimated likelihoods for both representations are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 11: The top subplot depicts the distance to the railing over the traversal, and the bottom one shows the estimated displacement, which is translated into heading correction. Positive displacement makes the robot turn left, and negative displacement causes right turns.

Secondly, we use the contribution matrix C from equation (16) to interpret the robot’s behaviour, see Figure 10. The robot can navigate using multiple features (e.g. bike lane and or railing). It is also visible that the visual model prefers more distant features. One reason for preferring more distant features is that they are typically more consistent. The second reason is that hypercolumns have a limited receptive field, making it impossible to use larger features. The neural network architecture can be altered to output hypercolumns with a larger receptive field, resulting in a preference for closer features. The VT&R stability analysis in [4, 5] indicates that the use of closer features results in faster

Fig. 12: The bottom plot shows softmaxed displacement likelihoods of two representations to the top image. This demonstrates the semantic localisation capability - here, the robot’s orientation. The units in the top image mark the pixel coordinates.

convergence, but it can negatively affect the reliability of navigation.

4.3 Experiment 3: Sidewalk Traversal

The following experiment is conducted in a less-structured natural environment to demonstrate application in a more complex autonomous navigation stack. The chosen Stromovka city park in Prague contains many sidewalks with different widths and surfaces. The objective of this experiment is to create the average representation of the sidewalk from a short 20m training path. The created representation is used for a roughly 600 m long autonomous traversal of the desired path. Figure 14 shows examples of training images.

The navigation stack used in the experiment is discussed in Section 3.4. The chosen trajectory contains four crossroads represented as nodes in the topological map. The robot

Fig. 13: Visualisation of the autonomous traversal. The image is only illustrative and does not represent any measured data. The aerial image of the park was taken by a drone.

Fig. 14: The image samples used to create the average representation for the sidewalk in Stromovka city park.

performs a left turn at each crossroad to traverse a closed loop. The presented version of VTAG handles navigation between nodes. Node detection is based on odometric information and semantic localisation. We use satellite imagery to estimate the distance between the nodes and the left camera to detect the sidewalk after a given traversed distance. The whole desired path is visualised in Figure 13.

Firstly, we create the average representation and place the robot at node A. The robot then uses VTAG to perform edge traversals in the middle of the sidewalk. The distance travelled measured by dead reckoning is used to initiate node detection. When the distance traversed is close to the edge length (± 10 m), the VTAG estimates the probability that the sidewalk is present in the view of the left camera. The node is detected when the average representation match from the left camera is higher than the estimate from the front camera. The odometric measurements and the fraction of the likelihoods obtained from both cameras are presented in Figure 15.

This time, it is not feasible to use LiDAR for ground truth measurement because the sidewalk does not have usable structural features. It is possible to use GPS to record the robot's position during the experiment. Still, without manual labelling is not possible to use metric trajectory to quantify lateral displacement from the visual cue as in the previous experiments.

Fig. 15: Node estimation (in red) shows the sidewalk detection likelihood ratio of the left and front cameras. There are visible peaks at the node locations marked by letters corresponding to the topological map. The blue dashed line is the odometric distance from the previous node.

4.4 Case Study 4: Curb following

The fourth experiment is conducted on a yard at FEE, Czech Technical University. Focuses on the precision of the control and comparison to the classic VT&R approach. The goal is to follow a curb on the right-hand side of the robot. The ground truth is measured by the Total Station Leica. The major difference between the compared methods is that the VT&R uses a dense map of the trajectory, while VTAG uses only a single representation. The method used for comparison is a publicly available version of VT&R [5] with an improved visual matching scheme [38]. The map images are presented in Figure 16, and the convergence rates are shown in Figure 17. The results of the experiment show that the presented method has similar convergence properties to VT&R. This is caused by the fact that the convergence speed of the appearance-based methods is mainly given by the structure of the environment and the distance of the visual features.

Fig. 16: The example images collected while mapping the fourth experiment.

Fig. 17: Distance to map measured for VT&R (Bearnav) and VTAG. The sudden peaks are caused by obstacles blocking the laser ray of the Total station.

4.5 Robustness Analysis

The latent space of the pretrained CNN was trained for robustness to environmental changes such as day&night or seasonal changes while preserving the sensitivity to changes in environment structure. This experiment evaluates the influence of the appearance and structural changes on the representation’s response. First, we test robustness to day&night variations using a long-term dataset collected at the outdoor vehicle storage of the Skoda car factory. This dataset fits the use case of our method, which aims at usage in large repetitive areas. The goal of the navigation in this experiment is to follow a fence delimiting the parking lot. Examples of training images, captured during a single cloudy day, used to build the average representation are shown in Figure 18. The average representation is evaluated against the test images, which are taken in different weather and daytime conditions and are shown in Figure 19. The responses of the average representation to the test images are shown in Figure 20.

The second part of the analysis is focused on robustness to structural changes. This evaluation uses training images from the experiment 4.3 shown in Figure 14 and the desired trajectory with structural changes shown in Figure 21. The robot traversed 800m with two failures in sections with the most prominent structural changes. Resulting in 400m average distance between failures. Note that this metric is heavily dependent on the chosen training and desired path. The responses of the average representation to the desired trajectories with structural changes are shown in Figure 22. We calculate a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) to provide a quantitative evaluation of the influence of environmental variations. The clean signal is obtained by auto-correlating the average representation $\vec{h} = R^{avg} \star P(R^{avg})$. The computed SNRs are reported in Table 3. The results show that the images with the most prominent changes yield the noisiest response. Both structural and appearance changes reduce the certainty of the likelihood estimate, but the structural change

also influences the position of the global maximum. This is expected behaviour because the path with significant structural change does not comply with the mapping requirement 1.

Fig. 18: The map images used for building the average representation for the Skoda dataset.

Fig. 19: The evaluation images containing various appearance changes in the Skoda dataset.

Table 3: Environmental Variations SNR

Conditions	SNR [dB]	Valid estimate
Sunset	21.64	✓
Bright night	10.84	✓
Dark night	9.79	✓
Rainy night	9.24	✓
Minor struct. change	11.38	✓
Major struct. change	9.67	✗

Fig. 20: Responses of average representation to various conditions in the Skoda dataset.

Fig. 21: The evaluation images containing structural changes in the Stromovka city park.

Fig. 22: Responses of average representation to structural variations in the Stromovka city park.

5 Discussion

Conceptually, the presented work stresses the benefits of the linear matching schemes for real-world robotic deployments. Most of the existing visual methods focus on non-linear feature matching and similarity estimation based on

various distance metrics such as MSE or cosine distance. Our experiments show that transforming the images into the latent space with linear properties can benefit the applications of pre-trained models for certain proxy tasks - in our case, the appearance-based navigation. In theory, the presented method can exploit any model that produces a spatially consistent representation with the aforementioned linear properties. This concept aligns with the latest findings in self-supervised learning, such as [43].

5.1 Preserving the Properties of Latent Space

The linear properties are provided by the inductive bias, which is directly built into the neural architecture. Specifically, the exhaustive evaluation of all possible horizontal displacements via the cross-correlation of dense image representations. This was first presented in [18] and then further extended using an optimised latent space in [38]. The fast progress of parallel computing enables computation of the exhaustive matching scheme using an on-board device. The assumptions used in appearance-based VT&R (locality, planarity) are built directly inside the neural architecture, making it possible to achieve the presented results.

The major benefit of using average representation in the VTAG paradigm is that the latent space of the visual model is not changed. The previous method applied gradient descent to obtain a fine-tuned model representing the visual cue. This fits into a popular workflow where a general pre-trained model is adjusted for a downstream task. Still, the fine-tuning can corrupt the pre-trained properties of the latent space, such as robustness to environmental changes. Note that the latent space of the model used is trained primarily for image alignment and secondarily for robustness to common environmental dynamics (seasonal, day&night).

There are multiple problems arising from fine-tuning the neural network for the downstream task. First of all, every neural network optimisation has multiple hyperparameters (learning rate, batch size, number of epochs, etc.) influencing the qualities of the obtained model. Moreover, there are widely known problems such as catastrophic forgetting and overfitting, which can negatively influence the properties of the pre-trained model. These problems become even more prominent in situations where there are not enough data samples available for fine-tuning. Finally, stochastic optimisation makes evaluation and reproducibility more difficult.

5.2 Limitations

The performance of our method depends heavily on the chosen deployment scenario. Navigation is reliable when the visual cue is clearly visible in the image space and consistent.

The presented approach is not suitable for use in feature-less non-repetitive environments. In these cases, it is impossible to comply with the mapping requirements presented in 3.2, making our method inapplicable. The visibility of the visual cue can also be influenced by occlusions. Our experiments show that minor occlusions caused by pedestrians are not problematic. However, it is not possible to follow a visual cue that is highly occluded. The navigation stack used does not directly offer any fallback behaviours, but the low-likelihood estimates can be used for failure detection. Losing the visual cue for a short time is typically not catastrophic because of the convergence properties of the appearance-based method.

All the discussed limitations also apply to the original VTAG method [9]. We show that using an average representation can yield similar results, but we do not provide a direct quantitative comparison. Reliability metrics, such as failure rate, are heavily dependent on the deployment scenario. Moreover, the original approach required large-scale data collection handled by a different autonomous navigation stack. Our method can be rapidly deployed using only the training images collected during a short teleoperated traversal.

6 Conclusion

We present an improvement of the VTAG navigation framework used for robot navigation in repetitive environments. The purpose of the paper is to speed up and simplify the process of creating a neural representation of a given visual cue, which the ground robot should autonomously follow. This is achieved by creating an average representation of the visual cue. The average representation can be created in real time without the need for time-consuming stochastic optimisation. Additionally, our approach is more data-efficient and requires only tens of images compared to previous work, which used a dataset with thousands of images.

The paper provides a theoretical justification of the viability of the average representation in a pipeline with a linear matching scheme. Moreover, the validity of the presented approach is verified in five different scenarios. The method is easy to implement, lightweight, and provides an end-to-end path following using uncalibrated camera images.

Acknowledgments This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth, and Sports CZ (MEYS) through the project Roboprox no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004590 and the Grant Agency of the Czech Technical University in Prague, no. SGS22/168/OHK3/3T/13.

Author Contribution ZR: Conceptualization, implementation, experiments, manuscript writing. TR: Experiments. JU:

Manuscript writing, proof reading. TK: Conceptualization, experiments, supervision, manuscript writing.

Code Availability The implementation of the framework and the recorded experiments can be found at <https://github.com/Zdeeno/vtg>.

Declarations

Ethics approval The research does not involve human participants, their data or biological material and it does not involve animals.

Consent to Publish The authors gave their authorisation for the publishing of this article.

Conflict of Interest The authors have no relevant financial or nonfinancial interests to disclose.

Appendix

Table 4: Notation table

Symbol	Description
I	Camera image
R^l	Live camera image representation
R^d	Desired path representation
R^t	Training path representation
R^{avg}	Average representation
R^*	Optimal representation
\mathcal{R}^d	Set of all desired representations
\mathcal{R}^t	Set of all training representations
$\vec{q}_{x,y}$	Hypercolumn at coordinates x, y
Δp	Horizontal displacement
\vec{h}	Displacement likelihoods
$P()$	Circular padding
$f()$	Pretrained CNN

References

1. Lowry, S., et al.: Visual place recognition: A survey. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* **32**(1), 1–19 (2016)
2. Chen, Z., Birchfield, S.: Qualitative vision-based path following. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics* **25**(3), 749–754 (2009)
3. Krajník, T., Pedre, S., Přeučil, L.: Monocular navigation for long-term autonomy. In: *Int. Conf. on Adv. Robotics (ICAR)*. IEEE (2013)
4. Krajník, T., Faigl, J., Vonásek, V., Košnar, K., Kulich, M., Přeučil, L.: Simple yet stable bearing-only navigation. *J. of Field Robotics* (2010)
5. Krajník, T., et al.: Navigation without localisation: reliable teach and repeat based on the convergence theorem. In: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE (2018)
6. Schubert, S., et al.: Visual place recognition: A tutorial. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine* (2023)
7. Krajník, T., et al.: A visual navigation system for robotour competition. In: *First International Conference on Robotics in Education, Bratislava*, vol. 1, pp. 95–100 (2010)
8. De Cristóforis, P., et al.: Hybrid vision-based navigation for mobile robots in mixed indoor/outdoor environments. *Pattern Recognition Letters* (2015)
9. Cox, J., et al.: Visual teach and generalise (vtg)—exploiting perceptual aliasing for scalable autonomous robotic navigation in horticultural environments. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* (2023)
10. Zhang, H., et al.: A low cost vision-based road-following system for mobile robots. *Applied Sciences* **8**(9) (2018)
11. Ding, C., et al.: Mobile robot's road following based on color vision and fga control strategy. In: *2006 6th World Congress on Intelligent Control and Automation*, vol. 1, pp. 3124–3128 (2006)
12. Ismail, A.H., et al.: Vision-based system for line following mobile robot. In: *IEEE Symposium on Industrial Electronics and Applications* (2009)
13. Miyamoto, R., et al.: Vision-based road-following using results of semantic segmentation for autonomous navigation. In: *IEEE 9th International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, pp. 174–179 (2019)
14. Nigam, A., Sanodiya, R.K., Joshi, P., Subhangi: Generalized visual path following on jetbot using normalization with reinforcement learning. In: *2024 IEEE International Conference on Advanced Robotics and Its Social Impacts (ARSO)*, pp. 247–252 (2024). DOI 10.1109/ARSO60199.2024.10557750
15. Maldonado-Ramirez, A., Rios-Cabrera, R., Lopez-Juarez, I.: A visual path-following learning approach for industrial robots using drl. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing* **71**, 102130 (2021)
16. Bingol, M.C., Aydogmus, O.: Hybrid learning-based visual path following for an industrial robot. *Robotica* **42**(11), 3888–3903 (2024). DOI 10.1017/S026357472400170X
17. E. Royer et al.: Monocular vision for mobile robot localization and autonomous navigation. *Int. Journal of Computer Vision* (2007)
18. Dall'Osto, D., Fischer, T., Milford, M.: Fast and robust bio-inspired teach and repeat navigation. In: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (2021)
19. Nitsche, M., Pessacq, F., Civera, J.: Visual-inertial teach and repeat. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **131**, 103577 (2020)
20. Furgale, P., Barfoot, T.D.: Visual teach and repeat for long-range rover autonomy. *Journal of Field Robotics* (2010)
21. Mattamala, M., et al.: An efficient locally reactive controller for safe navigation in visual teach and repeat missions. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* **7**(2), 2353–2360 (2022)
22. Sehn, J., Wu, Y., Barfoot, T.D.: Along similar lines: Local obstacle avoidance for long-term autonomous path following. In: *2023 20th Conference on Robots and Vision (CRV)*, pp. 81–88 (2023)
23. Lowe, D.: Object recognition from local scale-invariant features. In: *International Conference on Computer Vision* (1999)
24. Bay, H., et al.: Speeded-up robust features (surf). *Computer Vision and Image Understanding* **110**(3), 346–359 (2008)
25. Neubert, P., et al.: Superpixel-based appearance change prediction for long-term navigation across seasons. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* **69**, 15–27 (2015)
26. DeTone, D., Malisiewicz, T., Rabinovich, A.: Superpoint: Self-supervised interest point detection and description. In: *IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR)* (2018)
27. Camara, L.G., et al.: Accurate and robust teach and repeat navigation by visual place recognition: A cnn approach. In: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (2020)
28. Spencer, J., et al.: Same features, different day: Weakly supervised feature learning for seasonal invariance. In: *IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR)* (2020)
29. Sunderhauf, N., et al.: On the performance of convnet features for place recognition. In: *IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (2015)
30. Gridseth, M., Barfoot, T.D.: Keeping an eye on things: Deep learned features for long-term visual localization. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* **7**(2), 1016–1023 (2022)
31. Sun, L., et al.: Robust and long-term monocular teach and repeat navigation using a single-experience map. In: *IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)* (2021)
32. Anoosheh, A., et al.: Night-to-day image translation for retrieval-based localization. In: *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 5958–5964 (2019)
33. Chopra, S., et al.: Learning a similarity metric discriminatively, with application to face verification. In: *IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR)* (2005)
34. Bertinetto, L., et al.: Fully-convolutional siamese networks for object tracking. In: *European Conference on Computer Visions* (2016)
35. Germain, H., Bourmaud, G., Lepetit, V.: Sparse-to-dense hyper-column matching for long-term visual localization. In: *International Conference on 3D Vision (3DV)* (2019)
36. He, K., Fan, H., Wu, Y., Xie, S., Girshick, R.: Momentum contrast for unsupervised visual representation learning. In: *IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR)* (2020)
37. Chen, T., et al.: A simple framework for contrastive learning of visual representations. In: *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning, Proceedings of Machine Learning Research (PMLR)*, vol. 119 (2020)
38. Rozsypálek, Z., et al.: Contrastive learning for image registration in visual teach and repeat navigation. *Sensors* **22**(8) (2022)
39. Linegar, C., et al.: Work smart, not hard: Recalling relevant experiences for vast-scale but time-constrained localisation. In: *ICRA* (2015)
40. Churchill, W., Newman, P.: Experience-based navigation for long-term localisation. *International Journal of Robotics Research* (2013)
41. Rozsypálek, Z., Rouček, T., Vintr, T., Krajník, T.: Multidimensional particle filter for long-term visual teach and repeat in changing environments. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters* **8**(4), 1951–1958 (2023)
42. Fischler, M.A., Bolles, R.C.: Random sample consensus: a paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. *Commun. ACM* **24**(6), 381–395 (1981)
43. Zbontar, J., Jing, L., Misra, I., LeCun, Y., Deny, S.: Barlow twins: Self-supervised learning via redundancy reduction. In: *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning, Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 139, pp. 12310–12320. PMLR (2021)